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SOX4 and SOX15 are lineage commitment factors that specify the adenocarcinoma type of non-small cell lung cancer.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

We demonstrate through whole transcriptome analysis of the human lung and the solid tumor resulting in the highest number of fatalities world-wide, the adenocarcinoma subtype of non-small cell lung cancer, that the SRY-box transcription factors SOX4 and SOX15 are lineage commitment factors that specify the identity of the adenocarcinoma type while reinforcing the transformed state of the solid tumor.